

**The Insurance, Legal, and Financial Situation of Parents of Childhood and Adolescent Cancer
Survivors: A Systematic Review**

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Abstract

Background: Childhood and adolescent cancer affects not only patients but also their parents, who face challenges beyond the emotional burden, including financial hardship, insurance issues, and legal complications.

Aims: This review synthesized existing literature on the long-term financial, insurance, and legal circumstances of parents of childhood and adolescent cancer survivors (CACS).

Methods: A systematic search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and PsycINFO, complemented by forward and backward citation searches. Peer-reviewed, original studies were eligible if they examined financial, insurance, or legal hardships among parents of children diagnosed with cancer before age 18 and at least two years post-diagnosis. Following screening and data extraction, a narrative synthesis was conducted.

Results: Twenty-four publications on parents of CACS were included. All addressed financial circumstances, four covered insurance-related issues, and two addressed legal aspects. Parents often face long-term financial burdens due to ongoing medical expenses, loss of income, inadequate insurance coverage, and late effects of cancer and its treatment. Risk factors for financial hardship included child-related characteristics such as younger age at diagnosis, and parental characteristics such as being a mother or having a low level of education.

Conclusions: Even years after treatment, many parents continue to experience financial, insurance, and legal hardships. Mothers, parents with low education, and families of children diagnosed at a younger age, are particularly at risk. These findings emphasize the need for sustained support beyond treatment, systematic early identification of at-risk families, targeted education and policy-level interventions to alleviate long-term burdens faced by affected families.

Keywords: childhood cancer, finances, insurance, legal, parents, survivors, systematic review

Background

Parents of children diagnosed with cancer not only face family adjustments and psychological challenges [1,2] but may also encounter significant hardships in financial, insurance, and legal domains. Although these areas have received comparatively less attention in research, they can place considerable strain on families navigating the complexities of childhood cancer [3].

A cancer diagnosis profoundly disrupts family life. Beyond the initial shock and emotional strain, parents often face substantial financial and insurance-related challenges [4,5]. A considerable amount of research exists about the financial consequences for parents shortly after the cancer diagnosis and during treatment [6,7]. In the USA, families frequently encounter high deductibles and co-payments even when insured, as underinsurance remains a widespread issue, resulting in coverage limitations and significant out-of-pocket expenses [8]. In addition to medical costs, families also bear considerable non-medical expenses for food, travel, and accommodation during treatment [9,10]. As a result, many families are forced into debt or deplete their savings, placing them at risk of long-term financial hardship [11]. Beyond direct financial costs, indirect financial strains arise due to increased caregiving responsibilities. Parents often spend extensive time in the hospital with their ill child while simultaneously caring for siblings. These heightened caregiving demands frequently lead to changes in parental employment, such as reduced working hours or job loss, further compromising the family's financial stability [12].

While the acute financial impact of childhood cancer on families is well documented, less is known about the long-term financial circumstances after treatment. Existing reviews only provide partial insights: some refer to the long-term socioeconomic impact [13,14], whereas others do not explicitly address it [6,7]. However, there appears to be no review that has focused exclusively on parents of survivors and included only studies with a long-term perspective after treatment. In addition, previous reviews have concentrated on financial aspects, with limited attention to related domains such as insurance and legal challenges.

Against this background, it is crucial to recognize that the financial burden experienced by parents of CACS is multifaceted. To better conceptualize this complexity, the theoretical model

proposed by Jones [15] offers a valuable framework. It distinguishes between material and psychological financial burden, considers both healthcare-specific and general costs, and incorporates causes (e.g., treatment costs, employment changes), moderators (e.g., socioeconomic status, insurance type), and downstream effects on quality of life, mental health, and even mortality. Applying this model underscores the importance of examining financial hardship in relation to structural and systemic factors – such as insurance and legal contexts - and supports the need for an integrated investigation. Empirical evidence supports this perspective, showing that parents are affected not only by financial difficulties but also by insurance and legal challenges [16–18]. Given the interrelation of financial, insurance, and legal aspects, and the challenges in disentangling them, a comprehensive investigation across these domains is both necessary and warranted.

Taken together, the present systematic review addressed the outlined gaps by examining not only one isolated domain but the interrelated financial, insurance, and legal challenges faced by parents of CACS, focusing specifically on the long-term hardships. Accordingly, the present systematic review aimed to systematically synthesize existing research on the long-term financial, insurance-related, and legal situation of parents of CACS, including reported hardships, and their associated risk factors. It offers a comprehensive overview of the challenges reported in the literature and the associated risk factors, while highlighting key areas where further research is needed.

Methods

This review complies with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines [19] and was preregistered on PROSPERO (No. CRD42023423759).

Literature search

A systematic search was conducted in the electronic databases PubMed, CINAHL, Scopus, and PsycINFO using four search blocks: *insurance, legal, or financial hardships; survivors or parents; childhood and adolescence; and cancer* (Supplement A). The search strategy was adapted for each database to optimize the retrieval of relevant publications. Databases were selected based on their thematic focus to ensure a comprehensive identification of relevant literature across multiple

disciplines. This review included peer-reviewed studies investigating insurance, legal, or financial hardships experienced by parents of CACS. While the systematic search encompassed both survivors and parents, the present review focuses exclusively on parents. Findings related to survivors are addressed in a separate publication [20]. The initial search was conducted on March 16, 2023, and subsequently updated on June 24, 2024, and May 21, 2025. To find additional relevant publications, a forward and backward citation search was conducted on June 6, 2025, using Scopus.

Selection criteria

We included peer-reviewed, original research publications examining insurance, legal, and financial hardships faced by parents of children diagnosed with cancer. Eligible publications had to focus on parents of children who received a cancer diagnosis before the age of 18 years ($\geq 75\%$ of sample or separate analyses) and were at least two years post-diagnosis ($\geq 75\%$ of sample or separate analyses). The long-term insurance, legal, and financial hardships of parents of CACS were defined as the circumstances and demands that parents encountered in these domains at least two years post-diagnosis, that is, beyond the immediate treatment period. Publication selection criteria (Supplement B) were applied hierarchically to identify eligible publications.

Publication screening

Manual removal of duplicates and screening were done with the web-based screening tool Rayyan (<https://rayyan.ai/>). Titles and abstracts of all identified publications were independently screened by at least two reviewers (MO, PH, SK, KR). Full texts of potentially eligible publications were retrieved and assessed independently by at least two reviewers (MO, PH, SK, KR). Any discrepancies in selection decisions were resolved through discussion among the reviewers (MO, PH, SK, KR).

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed by the first author (SK) and independently verified by a second researcher (KR, MO). Detailed information on the insurance, legal, and financial situation, associated risk factors for related hardships, study characteristics (e.g., country, study design, sample size), parent (e.g., age at study, gender), and survivor characteristics (e.g., cancer diagnosis, age at diagnosis, time

since diagnosis), were systematically extracted using a predefined data extraction sheet. Information on comparison groups was recorded where applicable.

Quality assessment

The methodological quality of the included publications was assessed using the Quality Assessment with Diverse Studies (QuADS) tool, which is applicable to qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods study designs and has demonstrated substantial reliability and validity [21]. The QuADS tool comprises thirteen evaluation criteria, rated on a scale from 0 (not mentioned) to 3 (detailed information). Each publication was independently evaluated by two reviewers (SK, KO, MO). For each study and reviewer, a percentage of the maximum score was calculated, and the mean of the two reviewer assessments was used for analysis.

Data synthesis

To account for the inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative study results, we chose to use narrative synthesis for the analysis and reporting of findings [22]. Eligible studies were grouped by outcome domain (financial, insurance, legal) and risk factors to support the narrative synthesis.

Results

Publication selection

Database searches yielded 3,414 records: PubMed (n = 2,068), CINAHL (n = 686), Scopus (n = 423), and PsycINFO (n = 237). After removing duplicates (n = 962), 2,452 records remained for title and abstract screening. Of these, 354 full-text articles were retrieved and assessed for eligibility. Finally, 19 publications met the inclusion criteria. An additional 1,391 records were identified through backward and forward citation searching. After removing duplicates, 1,104 records remained for screening, leading to the retrieval of 110 full-text articles for eligibility assessment. Of these, five additional publications met the inclusion criteria, resulting in a final total of 24 publications included in the review (Figure 1).

Publication characteristics

Of the 24 publications included, the majority reported on quantitative studies (n = 14), while fewer publications reported on studies employing qualitative (n = 7) or mixed methods approaches (n = 3) (Table 1). The studies originated from 11 different countries, with most conducted in high sociodemographic index countries and one in a low-middle-sociodemographic index country [23]. Geographically, the highest number of publications came from Europe (n = 12) and North America (n = 7), followed by Asia (n = 2), Oceania (n = 2), and Africa (n = 1). The publication years ranged from 2004 to 2025, with 75% (n = 18) published within the last decade and 50% (n = 12) since 2020. The mean overall quality of the included publications was 82%, ranging from 73% to 87% (Supplement C). The inter-rater reliability was very high with an ICC ranging from .98 to 1.00 for the different studies, with a mean of .99 (SD = .007).

Reported financial, insurance, and legal hardships

Financial burden

Financial aspects of childhood and adolescent cancer were documented in all included publications and therefore reported across a range of countries. Studies highlight substantial medical costs from diagnosis through survivorship, which often result in long-term financial strain or instability for parents of CACS [18,24–28]. Families across different settings reported similar coping strategies and consequences: in high-income countries such as Australia and the USA, parents described depleted savings, difficulties covering rent, utilities, or unforeseen expenses, selling possessions, and in some cases relocating to more affordable areas or facing housing insecurity and homelessness [26,28–31]. In lower-income contexts, such as Kenya, families were likewise compelled to sell valuables, including livestock and land, and frequently accumulated debt [32].

In Sweden, nearly one in five parents still reported significant financial hardship an average of 15 years post-diagnosis [25]. Possible reasons for this persistent strain have been identified in other studies. For instance, evidence from Australia indicates that many parents struggled to regain financial stability after treatment because of their child's ongoing care needs [28]. A Canadian study showed

that parents often had to provide continued financial support well into their child's adulthood, as disability allowances were frequently insufficient to cover living expenses. In this study, 82% of parents reported providing additional financial assistance to prevent their child from falling into poverty, and 31% experienced hardship from out-of-pocket costs related to late effects not fully covered by insurance, including medication, eyeglasses, hearing aids, dental care, and vitamins [17]. Across contexts, parental finances were further strained when one parent had to reduce working hours or leave employment altogether [27,30].

Financial support for parents

Access to and the type of financial support varied across countries, significantly influencing parents' financial stability. In Switzerland, 4% of parents still reported a need for financial support an average of 24 years after diagnosis, compared to 8% shortly after treatment [33]. In the USA, the healthcare system provided financial relief when medical bills became unmanageable, with nearly 12% of families receiving such aid [27]. In addition to institutional support, close or extended family members were an important source of financial assistance [29].

At the same time, several shortcomings were reported. Lack of awareness about available programs contributed to long-term hardship [29]. Furthermore, many parents described the process of seeking support as burdensome or stigmatizing. For instance, 57% found disability allowance applications burdensome and felt poorly supported, and some reported being treated in a demeaning way when applying for public funding [17,27]. Families also faced uncertainty about the continuity of financial aid after treatment [29]. In some contexts, national policies created additional barriers: in Singapore, parents relied heavily on government-managed medical savings funds to cover the costs of late effects, yet restrictive regulations made it difficult to access these funds [18]. Reflecting these challenges, more than half of parents in Switzerland expressed a need for a dedicated contact point to assist not only with financial matters but also with insurance and legal issues [33].

Income loss

Ten of the included publications investigated income loss, with some reporting a long-term decline in parental income following a child's cancer diagnosis [28,32,34–39]. Publications from Scandinavian countries highlight gender differences in income reductions among parents of children with cancer. These studies report substantial and long-lasting declines in mothers' income, ranging from 6% to 14% lower than that of reference mothers five to six years post-diagnosis, while fathers experienced only short-term reductions, typically recovering within one year, and their total income largely remained stable [34,36,37,39]. In contrast, one Swedish study found that fathers showed persistently lower earnings, while mothers' earnings became significantly higher than those of reference mothers from two years post-diagnosis onward and remained elevated thereafter [38].

In Switzerland, parents reported lower household incomes and a higher risk of poverty compared to comparison parents, even eight or more years after diagnosis. Notably, this effect was observed only among couples, not among single parents [35]. In the USA, income loss frequently resulted in debt, long recovery times, and difficulties covering basic needs [30,40]. Beyond economic losses, parents reported a shift in personal priorities following their child's cancer experience. This led to a willingness to accept lower salaries in exchange for reduced stress and more time with their families [28].

Income protection mechanisms

In some countries, income protection mechanisms such as sickness benefits and parental leave exist to support parents who are unable to work due to their own illness or the need to care for a seriously ill child. A study from the USA indicates that the absence of insurance coverage for income loss contributes to long-term financial debt [30]. A Canadian study found that although the proportion of families relying on sources other than regular salaries—such as employment insurance and social assistance—decreased over time after diagnosis, 20% were still dependent on them at least three years after their child's diagnosis [41]. Legislative reforms in Denmark granting full salary compensation for parents of seriously ill children underscore the importance of such policies, as they reduced the risk

of low income among mothers of children diagnosed after the policy change, while no differences were observed for fathers [42].

In Sweden, sick leave provides income protection for employees who are unable to work due to illness or reduced capacity. Among parents of CACS, 16% reported being on full or partial sick leave one year after the end of treatment. Five years post-treatment, 19% had been on sick leave during the two weeks prior to assessment, with 30% of them absent for at least seven days [43]. Lasting up to five years post-diagnosis for mothers and up to six years for fathers, parents of children with cancer received significantly more days of sickness benefits than comparison parents [44]. A similar Swedish study found that mothers of children with cancer had up to 6% higher total income than reference mothers around the time of diagnosis, primarily due to sickness and childcare benefits. From the third year onward, however, as these benefits declined, their total income fell below that of reference mothers, resulting in a 7% deficit seven years after diagnosis. No such differences were observed for fathers [37]. Another key income protection mechanism in Sweden is temporary parental leave (TPL), which allows parents to take time off work to care for a sick child or accompany the child to medical appointments. Both mothers and fathers of children with cancer used TPL significantly more often than comparison parents, with elevated use observed up to five years post-diagnosis for mothers and up to six years for fathers. However, no association was found between TPL use and long-term income development [45].

Health insurance challenges

Five publications highlighted significant challenges parents face with health insurance coverage for their child after treatment, which is also often associated with financial consequences [17,18,27,29,31]. A key concern is obtaining coverage for necessary treatments and services. Nearly 8% of families in the USA experienced difficulties in getting private insurers to cover essential medical care [27]. Medical expenses associated with late effects of the illness, such as hearing aids or medications, are often only partially or not covered at all by insurance, resulting in ongoing out-of-pocket costs and a sustained financial and emotional burden for parents [18,29,31]. Parents also emphasized the importance of securing insurance coverage prior to diagnosis as a critical factor in preventing financial strain later on [18].

Some parents reported relying on employer-based insurance to cover costs related to their child, but this often comes with restrictive conditions. For instance, to maintain coverage, parents must remain employed, and their child must continue living with them. When their child transitions to independent employment, they often lack extended health benefits, leaving parents concerned about how future medical expenses will be covered. In some cases, these insurance constraints prevented parents from retiring [17].

Legal and discriminatory challenges

Two publications reported on experiences regarding legal challenges of parents of CACS [17,32]. In Kenya, some caregivers reported experiencing discrimination or rejection at work following their child's cancer treatment, due to the child's cancer history [32]. Legal challenges also emerged concerning disability allowances and insurance claims. Some parents required legal assistance to successfully apply for their child's disability allowance [17]. When confronted with employment discrimination against their child or insurance providers refusing to cover necessary medical expenses, parents had to act as advocates, often enlisting legal support to secure their child's rights [17].

Psychosocial aspects

The financial burden associated with cancer survivorship has profound psychosocial effects on parents. Parents identified financial hardship and insurance-related challenges as a source of stress, describing it as a great burden, contributing to long-term stress [29,32]. Some parents adjusted their employment trajectories in response to their child's illness, opting for lower-skilled jobs that were perceived as more manageable in the post-treatment phase due to post-traumatic stress [28]. Beyond immediate financial concerns, parents worried about their child's long-term financial security, particularly about what would happen if or when they could no longer provide the necessary financial support themselves [17]. These ongoing financial worries affected parents' mental well-being, contributing to anxiety and feelings of depression [26].

Risk factors for financial hardships

Eleven of the included publications specifically investigated risk factors of financial hardship [24,25,29,31,34–37,40–42], while none examined risk factors related to insurance or legal challenges. Financial hardship was found to be associated with multiple factors, including cancer-related, child-specific, and parental factors (Table 2).

Cancer-related factors

A younger age of the child at diagnosis was associated with higher medical costs and greater reliance on financial support [24,41], and greater income reductions, particularly in mothers [34,36,42]. Leukemia was associated with higher medical costs, greater parental income reductions, and a significant decline in mothers' earnings [24,36,42]. Substantial income losses among mothers were also linked to diagnosis of CNS tumors and germinal cell cancers [36]. Chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and surgery each increased medical costs in parents [24].

Child-related factors

Parents of male children had higher medical costs than those of female children [24]. Parents of children with severe post-treatment disabilities reported greater financial strain [25].

Parental factors

Younger parents and parents not born in the country of residence faced a greater risk of income reductions and adverse financial changes [34,42]. Citizenship status and/or being a member of a minoritized group, language barriers, and living in a rural area were also identified as risk factors for financial toxicity [29]. A study from Korea found that higher socioeconomic status (SES) was linked to greater medical costs [24], whereas another study from Australia found lower SES to contribute to long-term financial toxicity [31]. Parents with lower levels of education were more likely to experience income reductions, financial instability, and an increased risk of poverty [34,35,42]. Mothers with lower educational attainment experienced greater income losses and relied on higher sickness benefits for longer periods [37].

Parents with low income or unemployment prior to the diagnosis were at greater risk of income reductions [34], and disruptions in employment and income, insurance-related factors, and a lack of a safety net were additional risk factors for financial toxicity [29]. Among fathers, being unemployed or employed part-time was associated with an increased risk of poverty [35]. Mothers residing in intermediate or densely populated areas, those with children at home, and those living in dual-parent households and fathers living with a partner, regardless of marital status, were more likely to experience income reductions [34,37]. In terms of psychosocial factors, parents who reported having unmet healthcare needs were more likely to report increased financial burden [25]. Increased feelings of anxiety and reduced access to social support were associated with difficulties in affording basic necessities [40].

Discussion

This systematic review provides a comprehensive overview of the published findings on the long-term financial, insurance-related, and legal situation of parents of CACS. All publications addressed financial aspects, highlighting several key themes. Parents reported long-term financial difficulties and sustained income loss. While some research emphasized the value of financial support programs and income protection mechanisms, many parents reported significant administrative and systemic barriers when trying to access such assistance. Financial challenges were frequently linked to insurance-related problems, and a few publications also documented legal difficulties. Several risk factors for financial hardships were identified, related to the child, the diagnosis, and the parents.

Our review demonstrates that existing research has predominantly focused on financial issues. The long-term financial burden experienced by parents is multifaceted and aligns with the theoretical model of financial burden following a cancer diagnosis proposed by Jones [15]. We identified mechanisms contributing to this ongoing burden. First, families face substantial direct costs, including out-of-pocket medical expenses and co-payments [27]. Second, many parents assume caregiving responsibilities even after treatment ends [28], which may contribute to persistent income loss and elevate the risk of poverty [35]. Third, some parents continue to financially support their children well into adulthood, particularly when survivors experience late effects or chronic health issues [17,25].

Taken together, these findings highlight that financial strain often persists long after treatment and can undermine parental financial stability over the long term.

Financial hardship may also stem from income loss. Several studies across different countries reported persistent reductions in parental earnings [32,34,36,37,39], with several Scandinavian studies indicating that mothers are disproportionately affected [34,36,37,39]. This gender disparity is likely attributable to the fact that mothers are more likely to reduce working hours or exit the workforce after a cancer diagnosis in their child [34,46], a pattern that continues into long-term survivorship [47].

Given these enduring financial challenges, this review underscores the importance of financial support services and income protection measures. Financial assistance during the treatment phase has been shown to reduce long-term economic consequences [48]. Policy instruments such as paid caregiving leave, sick leave, and temporary parental leave - as implemented in several European countries - play a crucial role in protecting income and preventing severe financial hardship [37,42,44]. Nevertheless, while childcare-related benefits offered substantial short-term financial relief during and immediately after treatment, particularly for mothers, they were insufficient to prevent long-term income losses, especially once these benefits expired [37].

Another central finding is the interconnection between financial hardship and challenges related to insurance coverage. This pattern was also observed in caregivers of children with other chronic illnesses [49] and in our previous review focusing on CACS themselves [20]. High medical costs related to long-term follow-up care and treatment of late effects are often only partially covered by health insurance, leading to substantial financial strain [18,27]. Difficulties in covering out-of-pocket expenses were also observed during the treatment phase [11,50,51], and our review shows that these challenges frequently persist beyond the end of treatment, representing a long-term concern for many families [17,18,29,31]. Another consequence of limited insurance options is so-called *job lock*, where parents may feel obligated to remain in their jobs or delay retirement in order to maintain employer-based insurance coverage for their child [17]. Despite the relevance of insurance-related issues to long-term family well-being, we identified only a few studies addressing this topic. Further research is needed to better understand the scope and nature of insurance-related hardships in the context of childhood cancer survivorship and to inform the development of health and social protection policies.

Only two of the included publications addressed legal issues. In Kenya, parents experienced discrimination or rejection at work following cancer treatment [32], raising questions about whether similar experiences occur in other countries and cultural settings. Another publication highlighted how legal challenges often intersect with insurance matters, particularly in situations where legal assistance is needed to secure disability allowances or resolve disputes over insurance claims. While such claims typically concern the now-adult survivors, many parents reported feeling a continued responsibility to act as advocates and coordinate legal support on their children's behalf [17]. This finding underscores the long-term nature of the caregiving role, which for many parents does not end with the completion of cancer treatment or with their child becoming an adult.

While we aimed to identify risk factors for long-term financial, insurance-related, and legal challenges, we only identified determinants of financial hardship. Younger age at diagnosis and leukemia were associated with higher medical costs [24] and reduced parental income [34,36,42]. A younger age at diagnosis is typically linked to a greater caregiving burden, which may explain this finding [34]. The severity of late effects also emerged as a significant risk factor for financial strain. In studies involving CACS, a higher number of chronic health conditions was associated with greater financial hardship and elevated out-of-pocket expenses [20]. This association appears to extend to parents, suggesting that the health status of their child continues to influence the family's financial situation long after treatment has ended.

Parents with lower educational attainment, lower pre-diagnosis income, pre-diagnosis unemployment, or migration background were found to be at greater risk of income loss and poverty [34,35,37,42]. These socioeconomic factors appear to compound the financial impact of a childhood cancer diagnosis, placing already disadvantaged families at even greater risk of economic instability. Notably, these findings mirror results from the general population, where the same characteristics are associated with financial vulnerability even in the absence of serious illness [52,53]. This suggests that families affected by childhood cancer are not only dealing with the stress of a life-threatening illness but are also navigating pre-existing structural disadvantages that limit their financial resilience.

Implications

The reported long-term financial hardships faced by parents of CACS underscore the need for sustained comprehensive support beyond the treatment phase. This includes financial aid, employment protection, and accessible caregiving leave to reduce income loss and prevent long-term risk of poverty. While assistance programs exist, many parents face administrative barriers [17,27]. Simplifying application processes, providing proactive counseling, and tailoring support to the needs of CACS families are essential to improve access and reduce stress. Given that mothers are disproportionately affected by income loss [34,36], interventions must consider gendered patterns of work status and caregiving. Paid leave, flexible work arrangements, and return-to-work programs must be designed with this in mind. Clinical and psychosocial care settings should adopt systematic approaches to identify families at elevated risk of long-term financial hardship early on - particularly those with pre-existing socioeconomic disadvantages. Early identification is important for timely, targeted referrals to appropriate counseling and support services.

Social and healthcare professionals should be aware of the legal and insurance-related burden that often persists after treatment. Parents may require legal support to navigate insurance claims, obtain disability allowances, or address workplace discrimination. The integration of insurance and legal navigation services into survivorship care could play a key role in alleviating the persistent burden experienced by families.

Study strengths and limitations

A key strength of this review is its holistic perspective, combining financial, insurance-related, and legal aspects to capture the real-life complexity of hardships faced by parents of CACS. This comprehensive approach adds practical value for healthcare, social service, and policy stakeholders. Conducted according to PRISMA guidelines, the review included studies from multiple major databases and search strategies, identifying gaps such as the underreporting of legal and insurance-related challenges and providing a roadmap for future research.

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. Although the review followed a rigorous and systematic search strategy, extended by a forward and backward reference

search, no search of grey literature was conducted, which may have resulted in the omission of relevant studies not indexed in peer-reviewed databases. The included studies employed varying definitions, measures, and timeframes for financial, insurance-related, and legal hardship. This heterogeneity limited comparability across studies and precluded quantitative synthesis, and the risk of publication bias could not be formally assessed. Although the inclusion criteria required that the child's diagnosis occurred at least two years prior, it was not always clearly stated in the studies whether specific reported experiences took place during or after the treatment phase, potentially affecting the interpretation of findings related to long-term consequences.

Conclusions

This review highlights that parents of CACS often experience long-term financial strain, driven by income loss, ongoing caregiving responsibilities, and gaps in insurance coverage. Navigating insurance claims frequently requires legal assistance, adding another layer of complexity. Although some support mechanisms are in place, many families face significant administrative and systemic barriers in accessing them. Legal and insurance-related challenges remain underexplored in research, underscoring the need for further research. Particular attention should be given to parents with pre-existing socioeconomic disadvantages, who are especially vulnerable to persistent financial hardship and require targeted, accessible, and sustained support.

Statements and Declarations

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Authors Contributions

LM, MH, and KR secured the funding. The review was conceptualized by MO, LM, MH, GM, SK, and KR. MO conducted the literature search, while reference screening was carried out by SK, PH, MO, and KR. Data extraction was performed by SK and double-checked by KR. Quality assessment of the included studies was conducted by SK, KO, and MO. SK drafted the initial manuscript and prepared all figures and tables. All authors contributed to manuscript revision and approved the final version for submission.

Preregistration

This review was preregistered on [PROSPERO](#).

Data availability

No new primary data were generated or analysed in this review. The full data extraction sheet is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram

Note: ^a Combined search for survivors and parents. The hardships experienced by survivors are discussed in another publication (Ospelt et al., 2024).

Table 1. Overview of included publications.

First author (year) ^[REF]	Country	Study design	Sample size Parents (survivors)	Comparison group	Sex/gender distribution of parents	Mean age at diagnosis of child in years (SD/range) or proportions for categories	Mean time since cancer diagnosis of child in years (SD/range) or proportions for categories	Cancer type	Domains	Reported findings
Benedict et al. (2025) ^[29]	USA	Qualitative, cross-sectional	11 (11)	None	82% mothers, 18% fathers	Median = 6 years (NR/2-16 years)	Median = 14 years (NR/6-23 years)	Mixed	Financial / Insurance	Depletion of savings, including funds Insurance challenges as stress factor Uncertainty about continued access to financial support after end of treatment
Chae et al. (2020) ^[24]	Korea	Quantitative, longitudinal	NR (7317)	None	NR	0–4 years: 30.3% 5–9 years: 21.1% 10–14 years: 28.0% 15–17 years: 20.6%	Longitudinal data from year of diagnosis to 5 years after	Mixed	Financial	Burden of medical childhood cancer costs
Christen et al. (2019) ^[33]	Switzerland	Mixed-method, cross-sectional	478 (308)	None	59% mothers, 41% fathers	6.9 (4.5 / NR)	24.0 (7.1 / NR)	Mixed	Financial	Financial support need reported by 7.8% of parents after treatment and by 4.2% in the long term (on average 24 years post-diagnosis)
Christensen et al. (2024) ^[30]	USA	Qualitative, cross-sectional	48 (38)	None	69% mothers, 31% fathers	NR (NR/3 months–14 years)	NR (completed treatment at least one year)	Mixed	Financial / Insurance	Depletion of savings Debt Insufficient insurance coverage for income loss

Hiyoshi et al. (2018) [37]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	3626 (NR)	Yes (parents of children without cancer at a ration of 1:10)	52% mothers, 48% fathers	NR	Longitudinal data from one year before diagnosis to seven years after	NR	Financial	Long-term income reduction for mothers despite higher childcare-related benefits and sickness benefits
Hjelmstedt et al. (2017) [44]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	3'626 (1'899)	Yes (matched comparison cohort; N = 34'874)	52% mothers, 48% fathers	0-4 years: 40% 5-9 years: 24% 10-14 years: 20% 15 or older: 16%	Longitudinal data from one year before diagnosis to seven years after	Mixed	Financial	Number of days with sickness benefits was significantly higher for mothers of CACS compared to comparison parents from the year of diagnosis to five years post-diagnosis, and for fathers up to six years post-diagnosis.
Hjelmstedt et al. (2021) [45]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	2788 (1394)	Yes (matched general population parent cohort; N =27'110)	50% mothers, 50% fathers	NR	Longitudinal data from year of diagnosis to six years after	NR	Financial	Among parents of CACS, the rates of temporary parental leave remained significantly higher than those of reference parents up to five years post-diagnosis for mothers and six years for fathers.
Hovén et al. (2013) [25]	Sweden	Quantitative, cross-sectional	511 (551)	None	78% mothers, 22% fathers	10.3 (4.5/NR)	15.8 (5.1/NR)	Mixed	Financial	18% of parents reported a long-term financial burden
Howard et al. (2014) [17]	Canada	Mixed-methods, cross-sectional	46 (46)	None	NR	8.5 (4.7/2.0-16.5)	NR	Mixed	Financial / Insurance / Legal	Parents provide financial support to their adult children Insufficient disability allowances Burdensome disability allowance application process

										Insufficient public health coverage and insurance barriers. Employer-based insurance to cover child prevents parents from retiring Legal support to secure child's rights
Kelada et al. (2020) ^[31]	Australia	Qualitative, cross-sectional	56 (48)	None	89% mothers, 11% fathers	5.2 years (4.7 / NR)	2.9 years (2.3 / NR)	Mixed	Financial / Insurance	Out-of-pocket medical costs after treatment completion Depletion of savings Long-term financial toxicity
Lemmen et al. (2024) ^[32]	Kenya	Mixed-methods, cross-sectional	54 (54)	None	56% mothers 20% fathers 24% other caregivers	Median = 5 years (IQR 3-8)	Since treatment completion: Median = 42 months (IQR 28-64)	Mixed	Financial / Legal	Reduced family income Need to sell valuables Burden of medical cost Risk of dept Employment discrimination for parents
Limburg et al. (2008) ^[41]	Canada	Quantitative, longitudinal	222 (111)	None	50% mothers, 50% fathers	0-4 years: 39.6% 5-9 years: 12.6% 10-14 years: 16.2% 15-20 years: 23.4% Missing: 8.1%	3-5 years: 73.9% 6-9 years: 16.2% Missing: 9.9%	Mixed	Financial	Among families with children under 10 years old, 18% relied on income sources other than salary
Lindahl Norberg et al. (2017) ^[34]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	3626 (1899)	Yes (matched comparison cohort, 10 comparison families for each exposed family)	52% mothers 48% fathers	0-4 years: 40% 5-9 years: 20% 10-14 years: 24% >15 years: 16%	Longitudinal data from 1 year before diagnosis to 7 years after	Mixed	Financial	Significant income reductions for mothers up to 6 years after diagnosis and for fathers up to 1 year after diagnosis

Mader et al. (2020) ^[42]	Denmark	Quantitative, longitudinal	12'418 (7'066)	Yes (matched comparison parents N = 125'014 of 69'993 children)	55% mothers 45% fathers	<1 year: 6.3% 1-4 years: 19.3% 5-9 years: 20.5% 10-14 years: 17.4% 15-19 years: 36.5%	Longitudinal data from 1 year before diagnosis to 10 years after	Mixed	Financial	Higher risk of low income for mothers of children with cancer diagnosed in 1982–1999 compared to 2000–2014, after the revision of legislation for salary compensation
Mader et al. (2017) ^[35]	Switzerland	Quantitative, cross-sectional	722 (383)	Yes	53% mothers, 47% fathers	<1 year : 22.5% 1-4 years : 48.0% >4 years : 29.5%	<8 years = 41.8% 8-11 years =34.5% >11 years = 23.8%	Mixed	Financial	Lower income for parents of survivors compared to reference parents Higher risk-of-poverty for parents of survivors
Ochoa et al. (2023) ^[26]	USA	Qualitative, cross-sectional	15 (15)	None	93% mothers, 7% fathers	Range = 1-14 years	Length of time finished treatment: < 1 years: 26.7% 1-2 years: 13.3% 2+ years: 60%	Mixed	Financial	Financial instability Reliance on public financial assistance Financial burden leading to mental health strain
Öhman et al. (2021) ^[38]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	7'730 (3'865)	None	50% mothers, 50% fathers	9.0 (6.0 / NR)	Longitudinal data from 5 years before to 10 years after the diagnosis.	Mixed	Financial	After short-term negative effects on both fathers' and mothers' earnings, the long-term effects were negative for fathers and positive for mothers
Patterson et al. (2004) ^[27]	USA	Qualitative, cross-sectional	45 (26)	None	58% mothers, 42% fathers	9.6 years (Range <1-18)	Mean length of time since treatment completion = 4 years (range 1-9)	Mixed	Financial / Insurance	Financial strains Insurance coverage problems Financial help
Syse et al. (2011) ^[36]	Norway	Quantitative, longitudinal	3'263 (NR)	Yes (general population ; N = 1'227'908)	50% mothers, 50% fathers	0-4 years : 43.1% 5-9 years : 21.5% 10-14 years : 18.6%	0–2 years prior = 10.8% 3–4 years prior = 22.8%	Mixed	Financial	10% reduction in mothers' earnings of surviving children, becoming more pronounced over time since

						15+ years : 16.8%	Cancer 5–6 years prior = 19.7% >7 years prior = 46.7%			diagnosis; no effect on fathers' earnings
Tan et al. (2020) ^[18]	Singapore	Qualitative, cross-sectional	5 (4)	None	80% mothers, 20% fathers	5 years (4.0 / 1- 11)	5 years (3.2 / 2-9)	Mixed	Financial / Insurance	Out-of-pocket medical costs Difficulties in accessing medical saving funds
Vaalavuo et al. (2023) ^[39]	Finland	Quantitative, longitudinal	4939 (2'476)	Yes (N =14,326 mothers, N=14,250 fathers, and N=14,326 children from unaffected families)	50% mothers, 50% fathers	0-6 years : 45% 7-15 years : 32% 16-19 years : 22%	Longitudinal data from 4 years before and 5 years after the diagnosis.	Mixed	Financial	Income reduction was considerably larger for mothers than fathers, with 6% lower than comparisons for mothers five years post- diagnosis, and no difference for fathers from 3 years post-diagnosis onward
Wakefield et al. (2014) ^[28]	Australia	Qualitative, cross-sectional	78 (45)	None	56% mothers, 44% fathers	13.3 years (2.6 / 7 – 17)	Time since treatment completion: 12.5 years (8.3 / 1.9 – 27.7)	Mixed	Financial	Need to return to work for financial reasons Change in housing / need for relocation due to financial difficulties
Wikman et al. (2016) ^[43]	Sweden	Quantitative, longitudinal	152 (83)	None	51% mothers, 49% fathers	0–3 years: 24% 4–7 years: 29% 8–12 years: 28% 13–18 years: 19%	Longitudinal data from year of diagnosis to 5 years after the end of treatment	Mixed	Financial	16% of parents reported sick leave one year after the end of treatment, and 19% reported sick leave five years after the end of treatment
Wimberly et al. (2021) ^[40]	USA	Quantitative, cross-sectional	321 (321)	None	94% mothers, 6% fathers	4.4 years (4.4 / NR)	9.5 years (6.0 / NR)	Mixed	Financial	Lost income resulted in 11% of parents having difficulties paying for basic needs and 5% struggling to cover their child's medical expenses

Table 2: Overview of risk factors for financial hardships of parents of childhood and adolescent cancer survivors as described in included publications

Domain	Reported risk factors	
Financial burden	Cancer-related and child-related	Parental
Higher medical costs [24]	Male Younger age at diagnosis Leukemia Chemotherapy, Radiotherapy, Surgery	High socioeconomic status
Financial burden / toxicity [25, 29, 31]	Severe disability	Unmet health-care needs Low socioeconomic status Citizenship status and/or member of a minoritized group Language barriers Living in a rural area Insurance factors Lack of a safety net Disruptions in employment and income
Struggling to pay for basic needs [40]		Increased feelings of anxiety Reduced access to social support
Risk-of-poverty [35]		Standard education Not or only part-time employed
Income loss		
Income reduction [34, 35, 42]	Younger age at diagnosis Lymphoid leukemia	Younger parental age Not born in country Low educational attainment Low income before diagnosis Unemployed before diagnosis Intermediate-/densely populated area Children at home Cohabiting

Reduction in mother's
income [34, 36, 37, 42]

Younger age at diagnosis
Unspecified leukemia
CNS tumors
Germinal cell cancers

Low educational attainment

Risk of adverse change in
income [42]

Younger parental age
Not born in country
Low educational attainment

**Financial support for
parents**

Reliance on financial
support [41]

Younger age at diagnosis

Higher sickness benefits
for longer periods [37]

Low educational attainment

Note. CNS = central nervous system.